

Synthesis of 3,4-Dialkylisocoumarins and 3,4-Dialkyl-*N*-substituted-isoquinolones

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3,4-Dialkylisochromans (5a-e) on oxidation furnish 3,4-dialkyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins (6a-e). Treatment of 6a-e with *N*-bromosuccinimide followed by refluxing with triethylamine furnishes 3,4-dialkylisocoumarins (7a-e) which were converted into various 3,4-dialkyl-*N*-substituted-isoquinolones (8) by reaction with different amines. The isochromans (5a-e) were obtained by treating the alcohols (4a-e) with HCHO/HCl. Compounds 4a and 4b were obtained from hydratropaldehyde (3a) by Grignard reaction with ethyl magnesium iodide and *n*-propyl magnesium iodide respectively, whereas 4c, 4d and 4e were obtained from α -phenylbutyraldehyde (3b) by Grignard reaction with methyl magnesium iodide, *n*-propylmagnesium iodide and isopropylmagnesium iodide respectively.

ISOCOUMARINS have been found to be associated with diverse biological activities. Telang and Usgaonkar^{1,2} obtained 3,4-dimethylisocoumarins by cyclodehydration of α -methyl acetyl esters of benzoic acid in presence of H₂SO₄. The acetyl esters undergo hydrolysis during cyclodehydration. The hydrolysis competes with cyclodehydration thereby affecting considerably the yield of isocoumarins.

Singh and Srivastava³ reported a new route to the synthesis of 3,4-dialkylisocoumarins. To establish the general applicability of this route, five new 3,4-dialkylisocoumarins have now been prepared which have also been transformed into various isoquinolones (isocarboxtyrils), another class of biologically active compounds. The method (Scheme 1) involved the conversion of alkylphenyl ketones (1) into α -alkyl- α -phenylacetaldehydes (3) via ethyl β -alkyl- β -phenyl glycidate (2). The esters (2) were obtained from the ketones (1) by Darzens glycidic ester condensation, hydrolysed and then decarboxylated to 3. Treatment 3 with alkyl magnesium iodides furnished 1,2-dialkyl-2-phenylethan-1-ols (4), which were converted into 3,4-dialkylisochromans (5) by hydrogen chloride gas and formalin. Oxidation of 5 by chromium trioxide in glacial acetic acid or by selenium dioxide furnished 3,4-dialkyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins (6). 6 furnished 3,4-dialkylisocoumarins (7) on treatment with NBS followed by refluxing the 4-bromo derivatives, obtained after removal of the solvent with triethylamine for a prolonged period. 7 on treatment with liquor ammonia, ethylamine, aniline, *o*-toluidine, *p*-toluidine and α -naphthylamine separately furnished the corresponding 3,4-dialkylisoquinolones (8).

Experimental

M.p. and b.p. are uncorrected. Uv spectra (EtOH) were recorded on a Beckmann DU-6 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (neat/KBr on a Perkin-Elmer 577

1a, 2a, 3a; R¹ = CH₃
1b, 2b, 3b; R¹ = C₂H₅
4a, 5a, 6a, 7a; R¹ = CH₃, R² = C₆H₅
4b, 5b, 6b, 7b; R¹ = CH₃, R² = *n*-C₃H₇
4c, 5c, 6c, 7c; R¹ = C₂H₅, R² = CH₃
4d, 5d, 6d, 7d; R¹ = C₂H₅, R² = *n*-C₃H₇
4e, 5e, 6e, 7e; R¹ = C₂H₅, R² = *i*-C₃H₇
8; R³ = H, C₂H₅, C₆H₅, *o*-C₆H₄,
p-CH₃C₆H₄, α -C₁₀H₇

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) ClCH₂COOEt, (ii) OEt⁻, (iii) aqueous NaOH, (iv) R²MgI, (v) HCHO/HCl, (vi) CrO₃ or SeO₂, (vii) NBS - Et₃N, (viii) NH₃, C₂H₅NH₂, C₆H₅NH₂, *o*-C₆H₄NH₂, *p*-CH₃C₆H₄NH₂, α -C₁₀H₇NH₂

spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CCl₄) on a Varian A-60 spectrophotometer (60 MHz) with TMS as an internal standard.

1,2-Dialkyl-2-phenylethan-1-ols (4): Hydratrop-aldehyde⁴ (3a; 0.10 mol) in dry ether (25 ml) was added to the Grignard solution (prepared from 3.0 g Mg and 0.10 mol EtI in 25 ml dry ether) with stirring and the mixture was refluxed for 1.5 h. The ethereal solution was poured into crushed ice, acidified with dilute H₂SO₄ and extracted with ether (3×30 ml). The ether extract was washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and dried (anhydrous K₂CO₃). The solvent was removed and the residue was distilled under reduced pressure (4a; 85%), b.p. 102°/2 mm. Similarly other compounds were prepared: 4b (75%), b.p. 110–12°/3 mm; 4c (90%), b.p. 102–14°/2 mm;

4d (75%), b.p. 112–13°/3 mm; 4e (75%), b.p. 120–21°/3 mm. All the alcohols gave a broad peak at 3 400–3 480 cm⁻¹ (OH).

3,4-Dialkylisochromans (5): Dry HCl gas was bubbled in a solution of 4-phenylpentan-3-ol (4a; 0.05 mol), formalin (10 ml; 37%), concentrated HCl (0.50 ml) and dry dioxane (15 ml) for 3.0 h at such a rate that temperature of the mixture remained 50–65°. After cooling, it was poured into ice-water and extracted with ether (3×30 ml). The ether extract was washed with aqueous Na₂CO₃ and water, and dried (fused CaCl₂). After removal of the solvent, residual liquid was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish 3-ethyl-4-methylisochroman (5a). Similarly, other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 5 AND 6*

Compd. no.	Yield %	B.p. °C/mm	Mol. formula	$\lambda_{\max}$ nm	$\nu_{\max}^{**}$ cm ⁻¹	δ
5a	84	135/1.5	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O	245, 280	3 065, 3 005, 2 980, 2 910, 1 480, 1 410 (CH), 1 610 (Ar), 1 110 (etheral)	0.85–1.12 (6H, m, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃ , C ₄ -CH ₃), 1.70–2.05 (2H, m, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 3.65 (1H, q, H-3), 2.90 (1H, m, H-4), 4.75 (2H, s, H-1), 7.27 (4H, m, ArH)
5b	86	125/2	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ O	240, 275	3 060, 3 020, 3 000, 2 925, 1 490, 1 410 (CH), 1 612 (Ar), 1 115 (etheral)	0.86–1.14 (6H, m, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃ , C ₄ -CH ₃), 1.80–2.10 (2H, m, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 3.70 (1H, q, H-3), 2.95 (1H, m, H-4), 4.76 (2H, s, H-1), 7.25 (4H, m, ArH)
5c	90	85/3	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O	245, 260	3 070, 3 050, 3 015, 2 950, 1 410 (CH), 1 605, 1 590 (Ar), 1 105 (etheral)	0.88–1.15 (6H, m, C ₃ -CH ₃ , C ₄ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.82–2.18 (2H, m, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 3.68 (1H, m, H-3), 2.92 (1H, q, H-4), 4.75 (2H, s, H-1), 7.15 (4H, m, ArH)
5d	82	115/3	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O	250, 270	3 075, 3 020, 3 010, 2 925, 2 905, 1 480, 1 415 (CH), 1 610 (Ar), 1 115 (etheral)	0.85–1.18 (6H, m, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃ , C ₄ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.78–2.32 (6H, m, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃ , C ₄ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 3.71 (1H, q, H-3), 2.8 (1H, q, H-4), 4.78 (2H, s, H-1), 7.20 (4H, m, ArH)
5e	80	112/3	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O	245, 272	3 055, 3 035, 3 005, 2 930, 1 450, 1 405 (CH), 1 615 (Ar), 1 120 (etheral)	0.82–1.25 (9H, m, C ₃ -CH(CH ₃) ₂ , C ₄ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.80–2.20 (2H, m, C ₄ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.55 (1H, m, C ₃ -CHMe ₂), 3.70 (1H, t, H-3), 3.05 (1H, q, H-4), 4.76 (2H, s, H-1), 7.25 (4H, m, ArH)
6a	60(40) ^a	85/1.5	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O	260, 285	3 060, 3 010, 2 980, 2 905, 1 480, 1 420 (CH), 1 730 (C=O of lactone), 1 615 (Ar)	0.88–1.15 (6H, m, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃ , C ₄ -CH ₃), 1.80–2.00 (2H, m, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 4.50 (1H, q, H-3), 3.05 (1H, m, H-4), 7.86 (1H, m, H-8), 7.30 (3H, m, ArH)
6b	80(70) ^a	177–78/3	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₂	265, 280	3 075, 3 025, 3 010, 2 930, 1 490, 1 410 (CH), 1 725 (C=O of lactone), 1 610 (Ar)	0.86–1.20 (6H, m, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃ , C ₄ -CH ₃), 1.80–2.15 (4H, m, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 4.52 (1H, q, H-3), 3.10 (1H, m, H-4), 7.92 (1H, m, H-8), 7.30 (3H, m, ArH)
6c	80(65) ^a	165/2.5	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₂	265, 285	3 105, 3 025, 2 985, 2 945, 1 490, 1 420 (CH), 1 725 (C=O of lactone), 1 610, 1 595 (Ar)	0.88–1.22 (6H, m, C ₃ -CH ₃ , C ₄ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.95–2.10 (2H, m, C ₄ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 4.53 (1H, m, H-3), 3.00 (1H, q, H-4), 7.90 (1H, m, H-8), 7.35 (3H, m, ArH)
6d	80(65) ^a	170/3	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₂	260, 282	3 080, 3 030, 3 015, 2 930, 1 490, 1 410 (CH), 1 735 (C=O of lactone), 1 610 (Ar)	0.85–1.25 (6H, m, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃ , C ₄ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.90–2.30 (6H, m, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃ , C ₄ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 4.51 (1H, q, H-3), 3.10 (1H, q, H-4), 7.88 (1H, m, H-8), 7.35 (3H, m, ArH)
6e	85(70) ^a	170/2.5	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₂	265, 280	3 100, 3 045, 3 010, 2 925, 1 485, 1 410 (CH), 1 730 (C=O of lactone), 1 615 (Ar)	0.80–1.30 (9H, m, C ₃ -CH(CH ₃) ₂ , C ₄ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.85–2.25 (2H, m, C ₄ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.60 (1H, m, C ₃ -CHMe ₂), 4.49 (1H, t, H-3), 3.00 (1H, q, H-4), 7.90 (1H, m, H-8), 7.37 (3H, m, ArH)

*All compounds give satisfactory C and H analyses

**Neat, ^aMethod-i (Method-ii).

3,4-Dialkyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins (6), Method (i): A solution of chromium trioxide (12.0 g) in water (6 ml) and glacial acetic acid (50 ml) was added with stirring to 3-ethyl-4-methylisochroman (5a; 0.02 mol) in glacial acetic acid (60 ml) at room temperature and cooled occasionally by ice to maintain the temperature at 25–30°. It was stirred for 2 h at room temperature, then mixed with an equal volume of water and extracted with chloroform. The extract was washed with aqueous Na₂CO₃ (10%) and water, and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the solvent the resulting clear liquid was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish 3-ethyl-4-methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (6a). Similarly other isochromans were prepared (Table 1).

Method (ii): A solution of 5a (0.02 mol) in xylene (60 ml) was treated with freshly prepared selenium dioxide (7.0 g) and refluxed for 6 h. The hot reaction mixture was filtered and the residue obtained after removal of the solvent was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over neutral alumina (50 g), eluting the column with the same solvent. After removal of the solvent, the resulting clear liquid was distilled under reduced pressure to get 6a. Similarly

other compounds were prepared. Compounds prepared by both the above methods were identical.

3,4-Dialkylisocoumarins (7): A mixture of 6a (0.01 mol), *N*-bromosuccinimide (3.0 g) and benzoyl peroxide (0.03 g) in dry CCl₄ (40 ml) was refluxed for 3.5 h, the reaction flask being kept close to a 60 W lamp. The mixture was then cooled and filtered, and the filtrate washed with aqueous Na₂CO₃ (5%) and water, and dried (Na₂SO₄). After removal of the solvent, the residue was refluxed with triethylamine (50 ml) for 8 h and the solid left after removal of triethylamine was triturated repeatedly with ice-cold HCl (2*N*) followed by water, crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) to afford 7a. Similarly other compounds were prepared (Table 2).

3,4-Dialkyl-*N*-substituted-isquinolones (8): A mixture of 7a–e (0.005 mol) and ethanol (20–30 ml) was refluxed with liquor ammonia, ethylamine, aniline, *o*-toluidine, *p*-toluidine and α -naphthylamine separately for 2–3 h on a water-bath and left overnight. The solid, separated in each case was washed with dilute HCl and water, dried and crystallised from an appropriate solvent to afford 8 (Table 3).

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 7*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	$\lambda_{\max}$ nm	$\nu_{\max}^{**}$ cm ⁻¹	δ
7a	60	112 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂	280, 330	3 045, 2 985, 1 460, 1 415 (CH), 1 740 (C=O of lactone), 1 615, 1 590 (Ar)	0.90–1.15 (3H, t, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.28 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.50–2.80 (2H, q, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 7.95 (1H, m, H-8), 7.35 (3H, m, ArH)
7b	55	152 ^b	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₂	285, 327	3 095, 3 035, 2 935, 1 470, 1 410 (C-H), 1 742 (C=O of lactone), 1 615, 1 605 (Ar)	0.92–1.18 (3H, t, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.26 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.45–2.85 (4H, m, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 7.92 (1H, m, H-8), 7.30 (3H, m, ArH)
7c	70	133 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂	290, 320	3 100, 3 020, 2 950, 1 480, 1 415 (CH), 1 740 (C=O of lactone), 1 620, 1 600 (Ar)	0.95–1.20 (3H, t, C ₄ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.14 (3H, s, C ₃ -CH ₃), 2.48–2.80 (2H, q, C ₄ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 7.95 (1H, m, H-8), 7.35 (3H, m, ArH)
7d	60	146 ^b	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂	280, 325	3 090, 3 015, 2 925, 1 485, 1 410 (CH), 1 740 (C=O of lactone), 1 615, 1 595 (Ar)	0.90–1.25 (6H, m, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃ , C ₄ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.44–2.90 (6H, m, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃ , C ₄ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 7.90 (1H, m, H-8), 7.40 (3H, m, ArH)
7e	57	143 ^a	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂	275, 325	3 080, 3 010, 2 920, 1 490, 1 405 (CH), 1 740 (C=O of lactone), 1 610, 1 590 (Ar)	0.90–1.39 (9H, m, C ₃ -CH(CH ₃) ₂ , C ₄ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.45–2.75 (2H, q, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.90 (1H, m, C ₃ -CHMe ₂), 7.92 (1H, m, H-8), 7.35 (3H, m, ArH)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses. **In KBr. Solvent for crystallisation: ^aEtOAc-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), ^bEtOH–EtOAc.

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 8*

Sl. no.	R ³	Yield %	M.P. °C	Mol. formula	$\lambda_{\max}$ nm	$\nu_{\max}^{**}$ cm ⁻¹	δ
1.	H	65	185–86 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ON	235, 325	3 280, 3 065, 3 010, 2 985, 2 900, 1 690, 1 600, 1 460, 1 380, 1 350, 1 275, 1 220	0.90–1.17 (3H, t, C ₃ -C ₃ CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.25 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.45–2.75 (2H, q, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 7.90 (1H, m, H-8), 7.40 (3H, m, ArH), 8.50 (1H, s, NHCO)
2.	C ₂ H ₅	55	133–34 ^a	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ ON	285, 315	3 085, 3 015, 2 980, 2 910, 1 670, 1 610, 1 470, 1 375, 1 340, 1 250, 1 210	0.90–1.18 (3H, t, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.27 (3H, t, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.40–2.70 (2H, q, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 7.90 (1H, m, H-8), 7.35 (3H, m, ArH), 1.32 (3H, t, N-CH ₂ CH ₃), 4.16 (2H, q, N-CH ₂ CH ₃)

Table 3. (Contd.)

3. C ₆ H ₅	60	122-23 ^b	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON	290, 310	3 080, 3 020, 2 960, 2 905, 1 685, 1 605, 1 475, 1 385, 1 345, 1 255, 1 200	0.92-1.18 (3H, t, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.25 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.45-2.80 (2H, q, C ₃ - CH ₂ CH ₃), 7.25-8.20 (9H, m, ArH)
4. <i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60	112-13 ^b	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ON	282, 320	3 045, 3 010, 2 970, 2 910, 1 680, 1 595, 1 465, 1 370, 1 325, 1 265, 1 200	0.90-1.18 (3H, t, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.26 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.50-2.80 (2H, q, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 7.20-8.15 (8H, m, ArH), 2.38 (3H, s C ₂ -CH ₃)
5. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	65	205-06 ^b	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ON	275, 325	3 055, 3 015, 2 975, 2 920, 1 680, 1 600, 1 470, 1 385, 1 320, 1 255, 1 245	0.90-1.20 (3H, t, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.25 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.50-2.85 (2H, q, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 7.20-8.25 (8H, m, ArH), 2.35 (3H, s, C ₂ -CH ₃)
6. α -C ₁₀ H ₇	75	218-20 ^c	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ON	270, 330	3 045, 3 007, 2 980, 2 925, 1 675, 1 595, 1 475, 1 390, 1 330, 1 370, 1 240	0.90-1.90 (3H, t, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.27 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.40-2.85 (2H, q, C ₃ -CH ₂ CH ₃), 7.20-8.75 (11H, s, ArH)
7. H			R ¹ =CH ₃ , R ² = <i>n</i> -C ₃ C ₇			
8. C ₂ H ₅	60	145-46 ^a	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ ON	285, 320	-	-
9. C ₆ H ₅	65	178-79 ^a	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ ON	280, 310	-	-
10. <i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60	125-26 ^a	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ON	275, 305	-	-
11. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	65	186-87 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ ON	270, 325	-	-
12. α -C ₁₀ H ₇	60	183-84 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ ON	275, 330	-	-
13. H			R ¹ =C ₂ H ₅ , R ² =CH ₃			
14. C ₂ H ₅	70	204-05 ^e	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ ON	280, 330	-	-
15. C ₆ H ₅	65	140-41 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ON	290, 315	-	-
16. <i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	68	165-66 ^a	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ ON	280, 310	-	-
17. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	70	181-82 ^a	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON	295, 325	-	-
18. α -C ₁₀ H ₇	60	173-75 ^a	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ON	280, 320	-	-
19. H			R ¹ =C ₂ H ₅ , R ² = <i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇			
20. C ₂ H ₅	56	984-85 ^a	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ON	275, 320	-	-
21. C ₆ H ₅	52	282-14 ^b	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ON	280, 325	-	-
22. <i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60	165-66 ^a	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ ON	285, 315	-	-
23. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	55	174-72 ^a	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ ON	280, 315	-	-
24. α -C ₁₀ H ₇	60	132-33 ^b	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ ON	280, 310	-	-
25. H			R ¹ =C ₂ H ₅ , R ² = <i>i</i> -C ₃ H ₅			
26. C ₂ H ₅	50	196-97 ^a	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ON	275, 320	-	-
27. <i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	55	182-84 ^b	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ON	280, 325	-	-
28. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60	226-28 ^e	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ ON	275, 330	-	-
29. α -C ₁₀ H ₇	58	179-73 ^e	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ ON	290, 315	-	-
30. H			R ¹ =C ₂ H ₅ , R ² = <i>i</i> -C ₃ H ₅			
31. C ₂ H ₅	60	161-62 ^e	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ ON	285, 320	-	-
32. <i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	52	192-94 ^b	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ON	285, 320	-	-
33. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	50	197-95 ^e	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ON	290, 325	-	-
34. α -C ₁₀ H ₇	65	235-37 ^e	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ ON	280, 330	-	-

^aEtOH, ^bEtOAc, ^cEtOH-EtOAc.

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**In KBr. Solvents for crystallisation. ^aEtOH, ^bEtOAc ^cEtOH-EtOAc..

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